

PRODUCT PROFESSIONALS' PERSPECTIVES ON TRADITIONAL AND AI-ENHANCED PRODUCT BACKLOG PRIORITIZATION APPROACHES

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Abstract: *Product backlog prioritization is a critical to modern software development, yet the methods used in practice often remain ad hoc and heuristic - driven. While academic research has proposed numerous advanced techniques, empirical evidence on their adoption and effectiveness in real-world settings is limited. This study bridges the gap between theory and practice by combining a systematic literature review (SLR) with a survey of 287 product professionals internationally. The SLR categorizes existing backlog prioritization methods across eight methodological families and highlights a disconnect between the abundance of novel models and their practical adoption. Survey results reveal that traditional techniques are the most commonly used, although satisfaction varies, with some showing high variance and polarized opinions. AI/ML-based approaches are used infrequently, but there is strong openness among practitioners to explore these. The findings emphasize the need for better alignment between academic advancements and industry practices, clearer value propositions for AI/ML methods, and greater support for product teams in adopting new techniques. This research contributes to the field by offering an empirical foundation for understanding backlog prioritization trends, identifying barriers to AI/ML adoption, and outlining directions for future research aimed at improving the effectiveness, scalability, and human-centered usability of product backlog prioritization methods.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, product backlog, requirements prioritization*

1. INTRODUCTION

Product backlog prioritization represents the ongoing process of estimating the importance (priority) of product backlog items. Despite the critical role of product backlog prioritization in modern software development, traditional methods used by most product professionals face significant challenges in efficiency, consistency, and adaptability. Numerous algorithmic and data-driven prioritization methods have been explored in academic literature – including clustering-based, genetic algorithm-based, NLP-driven, and fuzzy logic approaches – but their practical adoption remains limited. As a result, backlog prioritization often remains an ad-hoc and heuristic-driven process rather than a systematically optimized one.

The emergence of AI-driven backlog management introduces both opportunities and challenges. AI can theoretically enhance prioritization by identifying hidden patterns, predicting impact, and automating decision-making. However, questions remain regarding the effectiveness, interpretability, and industry adoption of AI-assisted backlog management. Are AI-enhanced approaches genuinely superior to traditional methods in practice? Do product teams find them useful, or do they introduce new challenges such as explainability, trust, and alignment with business goals? Addressing these questions is crucial for understanding the role AI can play in product backlog management and its potential to reshape software development workflows.

1.1. Research gap and research question

There is a significant gap in research of the real-world adoption, perceived effectiveness, and prevalence of product backlog prioritization approaches, both traditional and novel. Existing studies primarily introduce and evaluate new prioritization models, while empirical investigations into the usage and satisfaction levels of established methods – such as MoSCoW, RICE, and WSJF – remain scarce. No research comprehensively examines how frequently product professionals adopt either traditional or novel methods or assesses their practical effectiveness in real-world product management contexts. This study aims to address this gap.

2. RELATED WORKS

After reviewing and selecting relevant documents, eight main methodological areas of focus can be defined for the research of novel requirements prioritization methods: clustering-based, LLM-based, NLP-based, Machine Learning-based, nature-inspired, fuzzy-based, genetic algorithm-based, and semi-automated methods. Traditional approaches to product backlog prioritization appear to have received limited to no scholarly attention.

Clustering-based prioritization methods aim to enhance the management of large and complex requirement sets by grouping similar items based on various similarity measures (Achimugu et al. (2014); Belsis et al. (2014); Kumar et al. (2022, 2023); Sharma and Kumar (2023); Yang et al. (2023)). NLP-based methods prioritize software requirements by leveraging natural language processing techniques to analyze, rank, and order backlog items (Izhar et al. (2024); Ko et al. (2023); McZara et al. (2015); Shafiq et al. (2021)). LLM-based prioritization methods leverage deep learning models like GPT and BERT to analyze and rank software requirements based on contextual relevance, historical data, and stakeholder preferences (Sami et al. 2024, 2025). Machine learning-based prioritization methods leverage predictive models and adaptive learning to optimize requirement ranking, reducing manual effort and improving accuracy (Avesani et al. (2004, 2005); Perini et al. (2013); Somohano-Murrieta et al. (2021)). Nature-inspired prioritization methods utilize optimization techniques derived from biological systems, such as ant and bee colonies, to enhance software requirements ranking (Alrezaamiri et al. (2020); de Souza et al. (2011); Del Sagrado et al. (2010)). Fuzzy-based prioritization methods leverage fuzzy logic to manage uncertainty and imprecision in software requirements ranking, making them particularly useful for subjective and evolving decision-making scenarios (Ahmad et al. (2017); Gulzar et al. (2017); Mishra et al. (2016); Mougouei et al. (2019); Sadia et al. (2019)). Genetic Algorithm (GA)-based prioritization methods apply evolutionary computing techniques to optimize requirements prioritization in software development by simulating natural selection (Ahuja et al. (2018); Marghny et al. (2017); Tonella et al. (2010)). Semi-automated methods integrate automation with stakeholder preferences and dependency modeling to enhance efficiency and accuracy (Chua et al. (2022); Gupta & Gupta (2018); Shao et al. (2017)).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-method approach that combined a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) with a survey of product professionals involved in product backlog prioritization. The goal was to explore both theoretical advancements and practical adoption trends in traditional and artificial intelligence-enhanced backlog prioritization methods.

Insights from the SLR and survey were synthesized to develop a comprehensive view of both academic innovation and industry practice in backlog prioritization. The results are discussed in the following sections to derive implications for product managers and to suggest future research directions.

4. RESULTS

Out of the total 307 respondents, 287 qualified as they participated in the backlog prioritization in the last 12 months. The majority work as “Product Manager” (56.1%), smaller percentage as “Product Owner” (9.4%), “Head of Product” (8.4%), “Product Consultant” (7.7%), and “Business Analyst (2.1%). There’s been a significant number of “Other” roles (16.4%), such as “CPO”, "Product Coach", "Director of Product", "Project Manager", "Program Manager" and so on where the majority of individual roles represented less than 1%, and a few around 2% or 3% of the respondents. Unlike roles, company sizes were quite equally distributed, ranging in size from 1-10 (15.7%), 11-50 (16.4%), 51-200 (23.7%), 201-1000 (16.7%), 1001-10000 (13.2%) and over 10000 (14.3%) employees. In terms of the professional experience, different brackets were similarly represented, ranging from 1-3 years (15%), 4-6 years (31%), 7-10 years (26.5%), to more than 10 years (25.4%) with only one underrepresented category of less than 1 year (2.1%). The majority of respondents hasn’t used AI or ML tools in prioritization but is open to trying it (63.4%), 23.3% used it occasionally, while 7.3% used it frequently and 5.9% did not use it and is not interested in trying. 42.5% respondents stated they were somewhat likely to use AI-assisted backlog prioritization tools in the future, 26.1% very likely, while 7.7% were somewhat unlikely and 3.5% very unlikely. 20.2% were neutral.

Our research shows that the most commonly used methods are MoSCoW, RICE, WSJF, Value vs. Effort Matrix, Kano Model, Critical Path, Opportunity Scoring, Eisenhower Matrix, Cost of Delay and custom formulas. Most methods have a median rating of around 3 or 4 (out of 5). Some methods, such as WSJF and Value vs. Effort Matrix have more spread-out ratings, suggesting a mix of strong advocates and critics. We

can conclude that while most prioritization methods receive generally positive ratings, some have outliers and a wider range of opinions.

Nearly 70% of the respondents haven't used AI/ML-assisted backlog prioritization, with 63,4% being open to trying it, and 5,9% not interested. 23,3% have used it occasionally, and 7,3% frequently. In terms of the satisfaction level with traditional backlog prioritization methods, no significant difference was found between AI/ML-users and non-users, beyond satisfaction with certain methods was wider spread in non-user respondents, compared to AI/ML-users which were more uniformed.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings from both SLR and the survey responses offer a nuanced perspective on the current landscape of product backlog prioritization with several key insights emerging.

Traditional methods are dominant, but satisfaction is varied. Techniques such as MoSCoW, RICE and Value vs. Effort matrices remain most frequently used approaches across company sizes and seniority levels, however satisfaction levels reveal more nuanced picture. While median scores were generally positive, several methods (such as WSJF, Value vs. Effort) showed high variance, with some practitioners rating them very low. This suggests that while these methods are well-known, they may not consistently meet the needs of diverse teams and product contexts.

Novel and AI/ML-assisted approaches show strong potential but low adoption. Despite a growing body of literature proposing novel and AI/ML-enhanced methods, real-world adoption remains limited. Only about 30% of respondents have used AI in backlog prioritization, and only 7.3% do so frequently. The most common stance is openness to experimentation, with over 60% expressing interest in future use. This points to a gap between real-world adoption and potential for novel and AI/ML-enhanced methods. The willingness to adopt new tools, with nearly 70% respondents likely to use AI/ML-based prioritization methods in the future, suggests that the industry is ready for more advanced prioritization support.

There is a gap between academic innovation and practical application. The literature reveals a wealth of novel prioritization techniques, but many remain underutilized in practice.

6. CONCLUSION

This study bridges the gap between academic advancements and industry practices in product backlog prioritization by combining a systematic literature review with a survey of product professionals. It highlights the widespread use of traditional methods like MoSCoW, RICE, and WSJF, while revealing limited adoption of AI/ML-based approaches despite growing interest.

The results underscore a need for better alignment between theoretical models and practical applications, as well as for enhanced guidance, tool usability, and training to support the adoption of AI/ML in backlog management. By providing empirical evidence on the current landscape and perceptions of backlog prioritization methods, this research lays the groundwork for future studies focused on improving the effectiveness, explainability, and accessibility of AI-enhanced prioritization techniques. Ultimately, this work contributes to more informed decision-making for product teams and encourages further exploration into AI's role in optimizing software development processes.

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